

Microstructural and Mechanical Insights into 1.2709 Maraging Steel Produced by Direct Energy Deposition

Angelina Strakošová^{1,2,*} (0000-0002-1276-7263), Daniel Kvapil¹ (0009-0009-0874-1050), Filip Průša¹ (0000-0002-6494-5084), Marek Vronka² (0000-0001-8270-5386), Petr Svora² (0000-0001-7357-2702), Pavel Lejček² (0000-0002-6870-0949), Dalibor Vojtěch¹ (0000-0002-6910-3206)

¹ Department of Metals and Corrosion Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

² Institute of Physics, Czech Academy of Science, Na Slovance 1999/2, 182 00 Prague, Czech Republic

³ Czech Technical University in Prague, University Centre for Energy Efficient Buildings, Trinecka 1024, Bustehrad 273 43, Czech Republic

*Corresponding author: Angelina Strakošová, strakosn@vscht.cz, strakosova@fzu.cz

Abstract

The present work focuses on the characterization of the ultra-high strength 1.2709 maraging steel produced by the Direct Energy Deposition (DED) technique, either in its as-built or as-built + heat-treated state. Scanning electron microscope micrographs and X-ray diffraction patterns showed that the heat treatment (namely solution annealing and aging) had minimal impact on the microstructure changes of the maraging steel. The material is characterized by fine cellular or dendritic microstructure containing several percent of the ductile γ -austenite phase in both as-built and as-built + heat-treated states. A small amount of the $\text{Ni}_3\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}$ intermetallic phase was observed even in the as-built state of the material. The heat treatment caused a substantial improvement of the mechanical properties through the homogeneous precipitation of nano-sized needle-shaped $\text{Ni}_3\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}$ intermetallic phase. Tensile yield strength increased from 753 to 1957 MPa, ultimate tensile strength – from 991 to 2024 MPa and microhardness – from 350 to 700 HV0.1. The present results are also compared with those obtained for the same material produced by the more commonly used Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) technique. Despite having a coarser microstructure with a presence of γ -phase than the LPBF-printed material, the DED-printed maraging steel exhibited greater precipitation hardening while maintaining 5% ductility after heat treatment.

Keywords: ultra-high strength steel, direct energy deposition, powder bed fusion, microstructure, mechanical properties, precipitation hardening

1 Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM, also denoted as 3D printing) is a modern and currently very attractive production technology in the field of powder metallurgy [1-3]. AM allows printing parts of complex shapes, including small or even porous structures, which can be easily and relatively quickly reproduced. Likewise, it is possible to individually modify the shapes of individual parts without significant complications and thus produce unique parts [3]. As an advantage of this technique, there is also no need to make post-production machining of the additively manufactured parts. Often then only the final surface treatment is sufficient [4, 5]. Due to the specific conditions that arise during printing, additively manufactured materials show different microstructures compared to conventionally produced equivalents [5, 6]. At the same time, their properties differ even when comparing products of different printing methods [7], which demonstrates the importance of thorough investigation of such prepared materials.

Direct Energy Deposition (DED) and Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) are the most commonly used additive manufacturing methods for metallic materials [8]. Both methods are based on the local melting of small material volumes using high energy density sources (laser or electron beams). As a result of gradual but rapid solidification, characteristic dendritic/cell microstructures are formed [9-11]. The main differences influencing the microstructures between the two technologies are the cooling rates and the powder particle sizes [7]. DED is based on the localized melting of raw material supplied as either powder or wire at the point of deposition by a laser, electron beam, or electric arc. The deposition head then moves gradually across the surface, building up layers of the material [12]. In terms of usage, the DED method additionally enables, for example, the repairs and improvements of already installed parts and the modification of the chemical composition directly during printing [4, 5]. It is also possible to print the parts using both powder and wire feedstock material unlike in the L-PBF method where only powder can be used [2, 8]. Moreover, in 2019 the market shares of L-PBF systems were much higher compared to DED systems (85% and 8.3%, respectively) [6]. Therefore, DED-produced materials are still not as well researched as materials produced by the today's most common alternative L-PBF method.

Maraging steels rank among the strongest materials produced by AM. A significant group of these steels – based on the Fe-18Ni system – have generally little tendency for thermal shocks and cracking, while absorbing well the laser source energy, which makes them one of excellent candidates for 3D printing [11, 13]. The 1.2709 (also denoted as X3NiCoMoTi 18-9-5, 18Ni300) maraging steel is the most widely used material of the Fe-18Ni group [2]. Apart from high strength and hardness, it also offers good toughness [14, 15]. This steel is characterized by good weldability [16], dimensional stability during aging heat treatment, as well as great machinability in the annealed state [14]. Its fundamental strengthening can be achieved through a simple heat treatment composed of aging that lasts for several hours [17-19]. The main strengthening mechanism is a precipitation hardening with intermetallic phases such as Ni₃(Mo, Ti) [20], Fe₂Mo [21, 22], η-Ni₃Ti [9], and Ni₃Mo [23, 24].

The application of AM to produce parts of maraging steels thus forms a very potent and industrially usable resource. For this reason, it is crucial to investigate and compare the circumstances of both L-PBF and DED printing methods. Currently, a large number of research papers are focused on the characterization of the structure and properties of maraging steels produced by the L-PBF. Some of them [13, 25-31] relate to the examination of printing parameters for the successful production of high-quality products. Many research papers relate to the heat treatment of the L-PBF-produced maraging steel. Several works [26, 32-35] describe the impact of the combination of solution annealing and aging on the microstructure and changes in mechanical properties. Other works [36-38] focus on the impact of aging alone. Also, many researchers focus their studies on the types of precipitates that are formed during aging [9, 13, 16, 39, 40]. However, only a few studies [20, 41-45] work with the steel prepared by the direct energy deposition (DED) method.

In this study, the ultra-high strength 1.2709 maraging steel produced by the DED technology is examined in terms of microstructure and mechanical properties changes depending on the two-step “solution annealing and aging” heat treatment. The results are compared to the equivalent steel produced by the common L-PBF method.

2 Materials and Methods

The 1.2709 maraging steel powder was used to produce samples with the DED technology. The powder was commercially purchased from Praxair Surface Technologies. The particle size distribution (PSD) was measured by Laser Scattering Particle Size Distribution Analyzer LA-960 (HORIBA, Ltd.). The chemical

composition of the steel powder was measured using the Inductively Coupled Plasma method by the supplier and is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Chemical composition of the 1.2709 maraging steel (according to the supplier).

Element	Fe	Ni	Co	Mo	Ti	Al	Si	Mn	Cr
[wt. %]	Bal.	18.1	9.0	5.0	1.1	0.1	0.1	0.02	0.09

Samples in the shape of cylinders with a diameter of 10 mm and height of 50 mm were produced by the DED method on InssTek MX-600 (COMTES FHT a.s., Dobruany, Czech Republic). For this purpose, the SDM800 optical module was used. The process parameters are listed in Table 2. A Spiral CF (contour filling) strategy was used to build the samples from the maraging steel powder (Fig. 1). The building strategy consists of printing in spirals always starting in the center of each layer. The “n” layers were printed clockwise while the “n + 1” layers were printed – the opposite way – counterclockwise.

Table 2. Parameters of the DED process.

Laser power*, [W]	Scanning speed, [mm/min]	Powder feeding speed, [g/min]	Flow rate of protective gas, [l/min]	Hatch distance, [μm]	Layer height, [μm]	Laser beam diameter, [μm]
300-600	850	2.5	15	500	250	800

* DMT – a mode, when the printer automatically adjusts the laser power so that the layer height is maintained while being controlled using built-in cameras.

Figure 1. Scheme of the DED printing strategy of the samples with the dimensions: diameter = 10 mm, height = 50 mm. (arrows show the printing direction)

The average surface porosity of the samples produced by DED (namely “as-built”) was measured by threshold method using ImageJ software both in the plane parallel to the printing direction (\uparrow) and perpendicular to the printing direction (\perp). Half of the as-built samples were heat-treated by solution annealing (820 °C/1 h, air cooling) and aging (490 °C/6 h, air cooling) according to the works of others [7, 33, 40]. For this purpose, a muffle furnace (Martinek MP05) was used. Heat-treated samples were named “as-built + SAT”. The relative density of the as-built + SAT heat-treated material was measured only in the (\uparrow) direction. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was used to determine the phase composition of the maraging steel in different conditions: powder, as-built and as-built + SAT. For this purpose, diffractometer X’Pert PRO (PANalytical, Holland, Co K α = 0.17929 nm) was used to scan the material, the range of 6–110° with a step size of 0.039°. The generator settings of the diffractometer were 40 mA and 35 kV.

The metallographic cross-sections of the samples were prepared by grinding on SiC papers (P240 – P4000), polishing on water-based polycrystalline diamond suspension with a particle size of 3 μ m and final polishing on colloidal silicon suspension (Eposil F). Etching reagent Nital 2 (98 ml ethanol and 2 ml nitric acid) was used to visualize the microstructure. A light optical microscope (LOM, Zeiss Axio Observer D1m) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Tescan Mira) were used to observe the microstructure of the 1.2709 maraging steel. SEM (Tescan Lyra 3) equipped with an energy dispersive spectroscopy detector (EDS, Oxford Instruments, 80 mm²) was used to detect the chemical composition of the structural components of the steel. The LOM micrographs of the metallographic cross-sections of the samples were used to calculate the width and depth of the melt pools. The SEM micrographs were used to calculate the cell sizes using ImageJ. Detailed microstructure observation of the maraging steel in as-built and as-built + SAT conditions was performed using transmission electron microscopy (TEM). For this purpose, a thin foil of each material was prepared using a focused ion beam (FIB) in SEM (FEI Quanta 3D FEG). Conventional TEM, high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), and selected-area diffraction (SAED) images were captured by Fei Tecnai F20 field emission gun TEM operated at 200 kV equipped with an EDS detector, which was used to identify individual phases. For STEM, Z-contrast imaging was performed using a high-angle annular dark field (STEM–HAADF) detector. FFT calculations of HRTEM images using the Digital Micrograph program were used to identify individual precipitates. The indexation of diffraction patterns was performed using the CrysTBox software [46].

To eliminate the potential influence of the anisotropic behaviour of the maraging steel, porosity as well as microstructure and microhardness were evaluated both in (\uparrow) and (\perp) directions. Vickers microhardness (HV0.1) was measured on the FUTURE TECH FM-700 machine with a 100 g load and 10 s dwell time. In each case, ten measurements were made to achieve reliable statistics. Tensile tests were performed in the (\uparrow) direction of the samples on the universal test machine Instron 5882. The tests (three for each material) were performed at room temperature with an initial strain rate of 0.001 s⁻¹. The samples for the tensile stress-strain testing (Fig. 2) were prepared by machining from the DED-printed parts.

Figure 2. The dimensions (in mm) of samples prepared for tensile strain-stress testing.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Powder characterization

Figure 3 shows the morphology and the microstructure of the 1.2709 maraging steel powder. It can be seen (Fig. 3) that the powder is characterized by different sizes and shapes. However, most particles are spherical and surrounded by small satellite particles on the surface (Fig. 3a, yellow arrows). This shape and presence of satellites are typical characteristics of powders produced by the gas or water atomization processes. However, satellite particles have been found to be detrimental to additive manufacturing due to their potential negative impact on the powder spreading during the process. To prevent the formation of satellite particles, it is recommended to use the plasma atomization method [47, 48]. According to the results of the PSD measurement (Fig. 4), the particle sizes ranged from 60 to 110 μm with a median size of 80.6 μm . This size range is significantly higher than the size of powders that are used for the L-PBF method of additive manufacturing of metal materials [33, 49]. As can be seen in Fig. 3b, the microstructure of the 1.2709 maraging steel powder is characterized by dendritic or cell morphology showing the presence of a few occasionally found pores (Fig. 3b, red arrows). This type of microstructure occurs due to a high cooling rate (up to 10^5 K s^{-1}) during the gas atomization process [50, 51].

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of morphology (a) and cross-section microstructure (b) of the 1.2709 maraging steel powder. (yellow arrows show the satellite on the powder surface; red arrows show pores)

Figure 4. Size distribution and cumulative curve of the 1.2709 maraging steel powder.

EDS analysis was used to determine the chemical composition of the cross-section of the steel powder. One can see (Fig. 5, Table 3) that the alloying elements are distributed inhomogeneously in the powder microstructure. Iron (Fe) and cobalt (Co) are distributed mainly in the matrix of the cell structure. Conversely, areas between the cells (cell boundaries) are depleted of the above-mentioned elements but are enriched with nickel (Ni), molybdenum (Mo), titanium (Ti), and aluminum (Al) (Table 3, points 1-4). Although Mo and Ti are known as elements that stabilize the ferrite phase in steels, during very fast solidification of the maraging steel they concentrate in the liquid regions, and upon cooling, they solidify into grain or cell boundaries. Here, their enrichment together with Ni enables the formation of the austenite phase [7].

Figure 5. SEM micrograph and EDS chemical composition maps of the 1.2709 maraging steel powder.

Table 3. Chemical composition [wt. %] of the 1.2709 maraging steel powder according to the EDS analysis.

	[wt. %]					
	Fe	Ni	Co	Mo	Ti	Al
1	61.60	19.52	9.71	6.60	2.33	0.23
2	64.39	17.93	9.40	5.95	2.14	0.19
3	63.97	18.05	9.42	6.61	1.84	0.12
4	63.36	18.33	9.94	6.19	1.93	0.24
5	67.81	17.56	9.42	4.30	0.71	0.20
6	67.45	17.17	9.35	5.17	0.72	0.14
7	68.76	17.08	9.32	4.16	0.66	0.03
8	68.28	17.39	9.59	3.85	0.71	0.18

3.2 Microstructure and phase composition

Figure 6 (black spots) shows the presence of pores in the microstructure of the as-built maraging steel, which is typical for additive manufacturing [6, 52]. Due to the presence of pores of varying sizes, it was decided to classify them into two groups: small pores with a calculated diameter of $18.4 \pm 3.2 \mu\text{m}$ and larger pores with a diameter of $66.1 \pm 5.0 \mu\text{m}$. Due to their regular circular shape, they can be considered as gas pores [6, 52, 53]. This defect occurs due to the entrapment of gas bubbles formed during material melting and its rapid solidification. Also, the porosity of feedstock powder (as shown in Fig. 3b) can be another origin of the gas pore trapping in the molten material [52, 53]. Therefore, it is very important to use defects-free input material and find the optimal printing parameters. The relative density of the as-built material was calculated to be 99.89 ± 0.03 and 99.94 ± 0.02 % in the (\uparrow) printing direction and perpendicular (\perp) to the printing direction, respectively. These results are in good agreement with the values of the relative density of the materials produced by L-PBF technology reported in Refs. [7, 30, 54].

Figure 6. Representative LOM images of the DED-printed 1.2709 maraging steel porosity in the direction parallel to the printing direction: (a) upper part, (b) middle part; (c) lower part of the as-built sample.

Figure 7 shows the LOM micrographs of the 1.2709 maraging steel microstructure in the as-built state that is characterized by the presence of melt pools. The melt pool boundaries copy the laser movement according to the scanning strategy used during the manufacturing process. The measured depth of melt pools is equal to $590 \pm 29 \mu\text{m}$. This means that laser power was strong enough during DED to melt not only the newly deposited powder layer with a height of $250 \mu\text{m}$ (Tab. 2) but also at least one already solidified layer beneath it. The maraging steel produced by L-PBF exhibits smaller melt pools ($60\text{--}130 \mu\text{m}$, depending

on the laser settings [7, 27]) compared to that produced by DED. The main reason for this trend is the difference between powder particle size and thickness of the deposited layer of the powder [2, 7, 55].

Figure 7. LOM micrographs of the as-built 1.2709 maraging steel (a) parallel to the printing direction and (b) perpendicular to the printing direction.

Figure 8 shows that the microstructure of the DED-printed material is characterized by fine dendritic or cellular morphology inside the melt pools. The average cell size was calculated to be $2.4 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$, which is coarser than the approximately $1 \mu\text{m}$ cell size formed during the L-PBF method [9, 56]. Such a difference can be explained by the cooling rate which is several orders of magnitude higher during the L-PBF process (up to 10^8 K s^{-1}), thus promoting faster cooling and heat dissipation within the material volume compared to the materials produced by the DED technique (cooling rate up to 10^5 K s^{-1}) [2, 6, 9, 53, 57]. The EDS maps of the chemical composition and the weight percentage of each element in the microstructure of the DED as-built material are shown in Fig. 8 and Table 4, respectively. It can be seen that the difference in the alloying elements distribution in the cells matrix and cells boundaries have the same character as it was in the case of the powder (Fig. 5, Tab. 3). Significant segregation of Ni, Mo, Ti, and Al at the cell boundaries occurs, while substantial depletion of Fe and Co in these boundaries is evident. This phenomenon was also observed in Refs. [16, 44, 58]. Moreover, the authors in the Refs. [7, 20] found that not only Ni but also Mo and Ti promote the formation of retained austenite phase, which is located in the cell boundaries or even melt pools of additively manufactured maraging steels (as above-mentioned in the case of the powder).

Figure 8. SEM micrograph and EDS maps of the maraging steel in the as-built state.

Table 4. Chemical composition [wt. %] of the 1.2709 maraging steel powder according to the EDS analysis.

	[wt. %]					
	Fe	Ni	Co	Mo	Ti	Al
1	65.70	18.78	10.20	3.15	1.80	0.36
2	62.64	19.64	9.96	4.27	3.37	0.12
3	64.46	19.75	9.56	3.72	2.34	0.16
4	63.59	19.34	9.46	4.38	2.93	0.29
5	65.24	19.40	9.66	3.52	1.95	0.24
6	70.05	18.02	9.71	1.28	0.71	0.24
7	70.05	17.91	9.68	1.62	0.59	0.15
8	70.39	17.37	10.02	1.36	0.62	0.24
9	70.15	17.83	9.65	1.49	0.64	0.23

Figure 9a presents the bright field TEM micrograph of the maraging steel microstructure in its as-built state. The SAED patterns of several grains were examined. All SAED patterns demonstrated the presence of the same body-centered cubic (BCC) structure of martensite. In Fig. 9a in the upper right corner, there is a selected diffraction pattern of the BCC martensite structure in the zone axis (ZA) [111] inserted in the picture. Moreover, some spherical particles were observed in the TEM micrograph (see Fig. 9b). According to the results of the EDS analysis, the particle depicted in Fig. 9b is enriched with Ti, Al and C. It can be said that the particles are incoherent precipitates formed during the printing process due to the very fast precipitation kinetics of these elements. The presence of precipitates based on Ti and Al was also observed in Refs. [9, 40]. Moreover, the presence of TiN was described in Ref. [43] and TiO₂ was found in the microstructure of the L-PBF-printed maraging steel in Ref. [17]. If there is nitrogen (N) present in the maraging steel, Ti reacts with C and N forming Ti(C,N) carbonitrides [59], which were not observed in our study. Figure 9c shows dislocation networks and a high amount of very fine precipitates. HRTEM micrograph shows several nanometers long needle-shaped coherent phases (Fig. 9d). In the HRTEM

micrograph (Fig. 9d), there is a corresponding FFT image showing diffraction spots of a fine precipitate inserted in the upper right corner. It was found that the interplanar distances (d-spacing) of spots 1 and 2 correspond to the $\text{Ni}_3\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}$ phase. On the other hand, d-spacing for spot number 3 matched mainly with BCC martensite, but with the precipitate presence also. Precipitates with a size of about 5–20 nm were also observed in the matrix of the 1.2709 maraging steel produced by the L-PBF technique [9]. The formation of precipitates during the additive manufacturing of steels is caused by the cyclic reheating of already deposited layers during the deposition of new layers. This process is called intrinsic heat treatment (IHT) and was also reported in Refs. [17, 41, 60].

Figure 9. Bright-field TEM micrographs of the as-built maraging steel (a), (b), (c), and HRTEM micrograph of a very fine precipitate (d).

Figure 10 shows the representative image of the pore distribution in the as-built + SAT heat-treated 1.2709 maraging steel. It can be seen that the distribution and size of pores in the maraging steel haven't changed after SAT heat treatment (Fig. 10), compared to the as-built material (Fig. 6). Moreover, the measured relative density of the heat-treated material was calculated to be $99.9 \pm 0.02 \%$, which is equal to the relative density of the as-built sample, $99.89 \pm 0.03 \%$. It is recommended to employ hot isostatic pressing (HIP) as an effective method for removing pores from the material.

Figure 10. Representative LOM image of the as-built + heat-treated 1.2709 maraging steel porosity.

Figure 11 shows the LOM micrograph of the as-built maraging steel after SAT heat treatment. It appears that the solution annealing + aging heat treatment has caused changes in the material microstructure. On the other hand, we can still observe the boundaries of the melt pools here (Fig. 11, yellow arrows).

Figure 11. LOM micrograph of the as-built + SAT maraging steel. (yellow arrows show the boundaries of melt pools)

Moreover, the detailed SEM micrograph (Fig. 12) demonstrates that the chosen conditions of SAT were insufficient to entirely dissolve the characteristic cellular microstructure of the studied DED as-built material. The same phenomenon was also observed in Ref. [20], where solution annealing (815 °C for 1 h. air-cooled) and aging (480 °C for 3 h. air-cooled) were applied to C250 maraging steel produced by the

DED technique. Nevertheless, these results differ from those found in the maraging steel produced by L-PBF, in which a complete dissolution of the alloying elements was observed after the solution annealing + aging heat treatment [18, 30, 33]. The difference in microstructure preservation can be attributed to the fact that the microstructure of the DED-produced maraging steel is coarser compared to the L-PBF-produced one. This means that it is necessary to extend the duration of the solution annealing at 820 °C or choose a higher temperature to obtain a completely homogenized microstructure of the maraging steel. The elements distribution (according to EDS analysis) and their weight percentage in the as-built + SAT heat-treated maraging steel are presented in Fig. 12 and Table 5, respectively.

Figure 12. SEM micrograph and EDS maps of alloying elements distribution of the maraging steel in the as-built + SAT heat-treated state.

Table 5. Chemical composition [wt. %] of the 1.2709 maraging steel powder according to the EDS analysis.

	[wt. %]					
	Fe	Ni	Co	Mo	Ti	Al
1	62.68	19.15	9.66	6.40	1.93	0.19
2	61.69	19.54	9.90	6.61	1.97	0.30
3	61.77	19.06	9.45	7.11	2.36	0.25
4	62.54	19.35	9.52	6.29	2.08	0.22
5	67.88	17.47	9.47	4.17	0.76	0.26
6	67.80	17.73	9.35	4.44	0.65	0.05
7	67.49	16.90	9.55	4.92	0.73	0.41
8	67.69	17.34	9.20	4.86	0.58	0.33

It can be seen (Fig. 12 and Table 5) that the distribution of alloying elements remains almost the same as in the case of the as-built maraging steel (Fig. 8, Table 4). However, the intensity of the presented alloying elements on the cell boundaries is much lower after the SAT treatment. It can be explained by the fact that cell boundaries started to dissolve during the solution annealing, however, the temperature of 820 °C for 1 h was insufficient to fully homogenize the still fine microstructure of the DED-printed steel, which was

coarser than that observed in the L-PBF-printed material. The same observation of reversed austenite in the martensite matrix was observed in the case of DED-printed 18% M350 maraging steel after being heat-treated [45]. It is also known [7, 14, 23] that Ni, Mo and Ti are involved in the formation of precipitates during heat treatment. Therefore, it can be assumed that the intensity of these elements is lower on the cell boundaries (Fig. 12) because of the creation of intermetallic phases within the material matrix during aging at 490 °C for 6 h.

Figure 13a shows the bright-field TEM micrograph of the maraging steel produced by DED after SAT heat treatment. Diffraction in several grains was evaluated to identify the phase composition of the as-built + SAT-treated steel. The diffraction pattern (from a place marked as “diff” in Fig. 13a) is depicted in Fig. 13b. One can see that next to the main pattern consistent with a BCC martensite phase, there are slightly visible spots of another diffraction pattern (Fig. 13b, yellow arrows), which may indicate the presence of a precipitate. A small amount of incoherent spherical precipitates is already observed in Fig. 13a (marked as “precipitate”). Most of them were equivalent to those presented in the as-built material showing also an increased amount of Ti and Al (Fig. 9b). However, some of the incoherent phases have different chemical compositions (according to the EDS analysis). Figure 13a shows the precipitate, which is enriched mainly with Mo that could be the Fe_2Mo intermetallic phase formed during heat treatment [18, 34, 41]. According to Ref. [38], Fe_2Mo precipitates form due to the transformation from the less stable $\text{Ni}_3(\text{Mo},\text{Ti})$ phase when exposed to aging temperatures.

Figure 13. Bright-field TEM micrograph of the as-built + heat-treated maraging steel (a), SAED pattern (b) corresponding to the area “diff” in (a).

Figure 14a shows the presence of a high amount of coherent needle-shaped phases in the as-built maraging steel as a result of exposure to the SAT heat treatment mode. The dimensions of these phases were measured to be approximately 3–4 nm wide and 10–20 nm long using HRTEM images (Fig. 14b). Similarly to the as-built material (Fig. 9c, d), the precipitate type was examined using the FFT pattern in the zone axis [142] depicted in Fig. 14c. The d-spacing measurement shows that the precipitates, which

were formed during solution annealing and aging heat treatment of the DED-printed maraging steel, correspond to the phase of $\text{Ni}_3\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}$. The formation of Ni_3Mo was shown as a consequence of heat treatment in Refs. [24, 30] describing the maraging steel produced by L-PBF. Besides Ni_3Mo , Ni_3Ti and Ni_3Al phases were also described in Refs. [9, 22, 51].

Figure 14. Bright-field TEM micrograph of the as-built + SAT heat-treated maraging steel (a), HRTEM micrograph of coherent precipitates (b), and the FFT pattern of the coherent precipitates (c) depicted in (b).

The 1.2709 maraging steel in the three states (powder, as-built and as-built + SAT) was also subjected to XRD analysis. The resulting XRD patterns are shown in Figure 15 and the semiquantitative phase composition is listed in Table 6. In all states, the presence of two phases (α -martensite and γ -austenite) is apparent in the material structure. However, the amount of austenite decreases when the steel is heat-treated (Fig. 13, green line). The $\text{Ni}_3\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}$ phase was not detected using the XRD method either in the as-built or as-built + SAT heat-treated materials due to the very small dimensions (several nanometers long precipitates. Figs. 9, 14).

Figure 15. XRD patterns of the 1.2709 maraging steel produced by DED.

Table 6. Phase composition [SemiQuant %] of the maraging steel according to XRD analysis.

	Phase composition [SemiQuant %]	
	BCC	FCC
powder	93	7
as-built	96	4
as-built + SAT	96	4

According to the results of XRD analysis (Fig. 15) and the microstructure characterization of the maraging steel in different states (Figs. 5, 8, 12), it can be said that the austenite phase is located on the cell boundaries (also denoted as walls in Ref. [18]), which are enriched by Ni, Mo and Ti. Moreover, according to Refs. [16, 20, 22, 43, 61], due to very fast solidification during AM processes, these elements concentrate in the liquid regions, and upon cooling, promote the formation of the γ -phase at the grain or cell boundaries in the case of 18Ni maraging steels. However, heat treatment caused a partial dissolution of cell boundaries (Fig. 12), which leads to a reduction of the γ -phase and formation of the $\text{Ni}_3(\text{Mo,Ti})$ -type precipitates in the material microstructure.

The phase composition of the DED-produced maraging steel (Tab. 6) is very similar to those produced by L-PBF methods – containing a high percentage of α -martensite and a lower amount of the γ -austenite phase ranging from 1.6 % up to 10.3 % [9, 51]. However, the situation changed after the SAT heat treatment of the material. It was found with the steel produced by L-PBF (Refs. [30, 33]) that the solution annealing temperature of 820 °C is sufficient to decompose the melt pool and cell boundaries obtaining a 100% martensitic structure. Conversely to the L-PBF-produced steel, some retained austenite remained even after solution annealing in the present study (Tab. 6). The same result was described in Ref. [20], where DED-printed C250 maraging steel was investigated. This means that the conventional combination of solution annealing at 820 °C for 1 h [11] is insufficient for a full homogenization of the α -Fe solid solution of the DED-produced 1.2709 maraging steel. Even the temperature of 830 °C for 1 h was not sufficient to dissolve the microstructure characteristics of the steel produced by the DED method as reported in Ref. [15].

According to Ref. [62], the beginning of the austenite formation in the L-PBF-produced maraging steel starts at temperature $A_s = 622 - 642$ °C and finishes at $A_f = 818 - 825$ °C. The temperatures of 623 °C (A_s) and 801 °C (A_f) were measured for conventionally produced 18Ni300 maraging steel in Ref. [63]. It can therefore be said that additively manufactured material needs higher temperatures for fully austenitizing and homogenizing the microstructure, which will transform into 100% martensite after cooling. Since the DED-printed material has a coarser microstructure, the temperature of A_f will probably be shifted to higher values compared to the L-PBF-printed counterparts. As stated in Ref. [62], complete dissolution and homogenization of the 18Ni300 material microstructure can be achieved by heating the material continuously to a temperature of 900 °C with maintenance at that temperature for 30 minutes.

3.3 Mechanical properties

Figure 16 shows representative stress-strain curves of the DED-printed 1.2709 maraging steel in the as-built (solid lines) and as-built + SAT heat-treated (dashed lines) states.

Figure 16. Representative stress-strain curves of the DED-printed 1.2709 maraging steel. (solid lines – as-built state, dashed line – as-built + SAT heat-treated state)

Table 7 summarizes the mechanical properties of the 1.2709 maraging steel produced by DED in the direction parallel (\uparrow) to the printing direction. As can be seen (Fig. 16, Tab. 7), the SAT heat treatment caused a huge increase in the values of mechanical properties doubling both the microhardness (HV0.1) and the ultimate tensile strength (UTS). The tensile yield strength (TYS) of the DED-printed material has increased more than 2.5 times as a result of SAT heat treatment. The same trend of mechanical properties improving after solution annealing and aging heat treatment was also observed in Ref. [45], which relates to DED-printed 18Ni M350 maraging steel. It is known [9, 14, 18] that precipitation hardening is the main strengthening mechanism of maraging steels. As is shown in Fig. 14, the steel was strengthened due to the formation of $\text{Ni}_3\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}$ intermetallic phase during SAT heat treatment. Another important fact is that as-built + SAT-treated steel still maintains a relatively high percent of ductility, perhaps, due to the presence of the γ -austenite phase in the microstructure (Tab. 6).

Table 7. Mechanical properties of the 1.2709 maraging steel depending on the manufacturing method and heat treatment. (UTS – ultimate tensile strength. TYS – tensile yield strength. A – elongation. HV – Vickers microhardness)

	UTS [MPa]	TYS [MPa]	A [%]	HV0.1*	HV0.1 [^]
DED	991 ± 20	753 ± 51	18 ± 7	353 ± 8	350 ± 7
DED + SAT	2024 ± 44	1957 ± 51	5 ± 3	680 ± 11	700 ± 16
L-PBF [25, 33, 36, 38, 64, 65]	1012–1290	892–1214	11–18	360–400	–
L-PBF + SAT [65]	1974.9 ± 14.5	1939.7 ± 2.4	2.5 ± 0.3	about 600 [33]	–
L-PBF + SAT [#] [26]	1850	1750	5.1	–	–

* (\uparrow) direction; [^] (\perp) direction

SAT[#] (solution annealing 830 °C/1 h + aging 490 °C/6 h)

As can be seen in Table 7, the DED-printed maraging steel is characterized by lower values of mechanical properties (UTS, TYS, HV) compared to the steel produced by L-PBF. This difference can be explained by the finer microstructure of the L-PBF-printed material compared to the DED-printed counterpart (see Figs. 7 and 8 above). The difference in the elongation in this case is almost negligible, both materials have ductile

structures consisting of the relatively soft low-carbon martensite [9, 66] and γ -austenite phase. The situation changed drastically after the SAT heat treatment. Table 7 shows that the SAT has caused a higher degree of strengthening in the case of the DED-produced material than the L-PBF one. The difference can be caused by different Ti concentrations in the maraging steel. In our study, the input powder has a relatively high Ti content, 1.1 wt. % (see Table 1). Conversely, the powder described in Refs. [33, 65] contains 0.64 wt.% of Ti. A tremendous effect of the Ti content on the yield strength of the 1.2709 maraging steel is shown in equation (1) [59]:

$$\text{YS (MPa)} = 104 + 63 (\text{wt. \% Co}) + 195 (\text{wt. \% Mo}) + 552 (\text{wt. \% Ti}) \quad (1)$$

Besides the significant strengthening effect [39, 61], even the trace amount of Ti addition helps to prevent the coarsening of the austenitic grains [67, 68]. Moreover, it is known [69] that Ti has a good affinity to C and N forming carbides, nitrides or carbonitrides during steel production. During the heat treatment, Ti with Ni and Mo form Ni_3Ti [31, 39] or $\text{Ni}_3(\text{Ti},\text{Mo})$ [18] precipitates that strengthen maraging steels.

According to equation (1) and the chemical composition (Table 1 and Ref. [65]), the YS of the DED-printed + SAT heat-treated and L-PBF-printed + SAT heat-treated maraging steel should be equal to 2253 MPa and 1999 MPa, respectively. These values, however, differ from the experimentally obtained values of YS (Table 7). According to Ref. [70], the strengthening of maraging steel has a complex character and depends not only on the chemical composition, but YS is usually a combination of solid solution strengthening (σ_{ss}), grain refinement (σ_{gr}), precipitation hardening (σ_{ph}), and dislocation strengthening (σ_{ds}), as shown in equation (2):

$$\text{YS} = \sigma_{ss} + \sigma_{gr} + \sigma_{ph} + \sigma_{ds} \quad (2)$$

Also, it should be pointed out that the authors of work [70] described the strength development of the commercial hot-forged 18Ni(350) maraging steel. They found that the experimentally obtained (2376 MPa) and calculated (2390 MPa) values of YS were very similar. That could be a result of the fully dense martensitic structure. However, in the case of additively manufactured maraging steel, the YS calculation will have a more complex character than that of conventionally produced counterparts.

The Fleischer's equation (3) shows the solid solution contribution to the total strengthening of maraging steel [70, 71]:

$$\sigma_{ss} = \Sigma(\beta_i^2 x_{ia})^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (3)$$

where x_{ia} is the atomic fraction of solid-solution element, i , in the matrix, α , and β is the strengthening constant of element i to Fe. According to Ref. [70], the Ti and Mo have the largest strengthening effect with the constant values of 2628 and 2143, respectively; on the other hand, Ni and Co have the same contribution with the same constant value of 334. It is easy to calculate σ_{ss} of the L-PBF maraging steel, which is fully martensitic, while it should be considered that the DED-printed steel contains some amount of reversed austenite, which is, by the way, enriched with Ni, Mo and Ti in maraging steel. It means that the martensitic matrix is in some way depleted with these elements. Therefore, it can be claimed that the contribution of σ_{ss} is higher in L-PBF than in DED-produced maraging steel.

The Hall-Petch equation (4) estimates the contribution of grain refinement:

$$\sigma_{gr} = \sigma_0 + k_y d^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (4)$$

where σ_0 is the YS of a material matrix (for Fe it is equal to 50 MPa [70]), k_y is the grain refinement strengthening coefficient and d is a grain size. Due to the smaller grain sizes of materials produced through

L-PBF in comparison to those produced through DED [72], their contribution to the overall material strengthening, denoted as σ_{gr} , is expected to be significantly higher.

The Orowan equation (5) can be employed to estimate the contribution of precipitation strengthening:

$$\sigma_{ph} = \frac{Gb\varphi}{2\pi(\lambda-d)} \ln\left(\frac{\lambda-d}{2b}\right), \quad (5)$$

where G is shear modulus, b – Burgers vector, λ – the spacing between precipitates and d – their size (diameter), φ depends on the Poisson's ratio. As indicated in equation (5), the quantity and nature of precipitates are critical factors in determining the contribution of precipitation strengthening. This underscores the importance of accurate characterization and understanding of precipitate microstructures for precise estimation of their strengthening effects. Moreover, for materials produced using various methods where thermal history significantly influences precipitate formation.

Taylor's equation (6) shows the contribution of the dislocation strengthening of materials:

$$\sigma_{ds} = MaGb\rho^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (6)$$

where M and a , are the Taylor factor and empiric constant, respectively. These contributions are almost the same for both, the L-PBF and DED-printed 1.2709 maraging steel. The largest contribution to strengthening has the dislocation density marked as ρ in equation (6). According to Ref. [57] the increased thermal gradients observed in L-PBF components are associated with greater dislocation densities, and therefore with a higher σ_{ds} , in comparison to those present in DED counterparts.

Considering equations (2 – 6) it can be inferred that the calculation of L-PBF maraging steel strengthening is easier because of fully martensitic microstructure after being SAT heat-treated. As a result, the YS calculated using equation (1) closely aligns with experimentally obtained values. A significant difference between theoretical and experimental YS values of DED maraging steel can be attributed to the presence of defects in the microstructure. Moreover, this microstructure consists of a martensite matrix containing several percent of the austenite phase, leading to a more complex material behavior. A comparison of the mechanical properties of the micro and macro scales can prove that phenomenon. The highest difference between the mechanical properties of DED-printed vs L-PBF-printed maraging steel (Table 7) is observed in the microhardness values (about 100 HV0.1). The minor discrepancies in UTS, TYS and A values between the two materials may be caused by the larger tested area during tensile tests, which would contain more structure defects.

Figure 17 shows the fracture surfaces of the 1.2709 maraging steel produced by the DED method. As can be seen in Figs. 17a, c, the as-built material exhibits a more deformed fracture surface (in terms of size and shape) than the as-built after the SAT heat treatment. A similar feature of these two states of the material is the presence of structure defects, namely pores. High magnification SEM micrographs (Figs. 17b, d) show that both as-built and as-built + SAT maraging steel fracture surfaces have a dimple-like morphology characteristic of ductile materials [18, 38].

Figure 17. SEM micrographs of the fracture surfaces of the (a, b) as-built, (c, d) as-built + SAT maraging steel produced by DED. (red arrows show pores)

4 Conclusions

The detailed characterization of the ultra-high strength 1.2709 maraging steel produced by additive manufacturing using the DED technique, either in its as-built or as-built + heat-treated state, is described and discussed in this work. The results are also compared to the same material produced by the L-PBF. The obtained results can be summarized as follows:

- The DED technique allows the production of almost fully dense 1.2709 maraging steel with an average relative density of approximately 99.9%.

- The DED-printed maraging steel showed cellular or dendritic microstructure characteristics of additively manufactured steels. An average cell size of $2.4 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ and an estimated melt pool depth of $590 \pm 29 \mu\text{m}$ were measured to be several times larger compared to the steel produced by the L-PBF technique.
- The first step of the chosen heat treatment, namely solution annealing at $820 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h}$, was found insufficient to dissolve the characteristic fine cellular microstructure of the DED-printed maraging steel and transform it to a 100% martensitic as it was observed in the L-PBF-printed one.
- The intermetallic phase of $\text{Ni}_3\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}$ was observed in the DED-printed steel in both as-built and as-built + SAT heat-treated conditions.
- The DED-printed steel exhibited lower values of TYS, UTS and HV0.1 compared to the L-PBF-produced equivalent due to the coarser microstructure. However, the SAT heat treatment caused extended precipitation hardening of the DED-produced material with the $\text{Ni}_3\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{Ti}_{0.5}$ intermetallic phase compared to the L-PBF-produced material, which hardened with the Ni_3Mo phase.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Angelina Strakosova: Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Daniel Kvapil:** Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Filip Průša:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Marek Vronka:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Petr Svora:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Pavel Lejček:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Dalibor Vojtěch:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability Statement

The data used in this manuscript are available in the Zenodo repository at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14056749>.

Acknowledgments This publication was supported by the project "Mechanical Engineering of Biological and Bio-inspired Systems", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research. It was also supported from the grant of Specific university research – grant No A1_FCHT_2024_007. We acknowledge CzechNanoLab Research Infrastructure supported by MEYS CR (LM2023051).

References

- [1] V. Madhavadas, D. Srivastava, U. Chadha, S. Aravind Raj, M.T.H. Sultan, F.S. Shahar, A.U.M. Shah, A review on metal additive manufacturing for intricately shaped aerospace components, *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology* 39 (2022) 18-36.
- [2] D. Herzog, V. Seyda, E. Wycisk, C. Emmelmann, Additive manufacturing of metals, *Acta Materialia* 117 (2016) 371-392.
- [3] T.D. Ngo, A. Kashani, G. Imbalzano, K.T.Q. Nguyen, D. Hui, Additive manufacturing (3D printing): A review of materials, methods, applications and challenges, *Composites Part B: Engineering* 143 (2018) 172-196.
- [4] C. Cai, K. Zhou, Chapter 7 - Metal additive manufacturing, in: C.D. Patel, C.-H. Chen (Eds.), *Digital Manufacturing*, Elsevier2022, pp. 247-298.

- [5] G.M. Karthik, H.S. Kim, Heterogeneous Aspects of Additive Manufactured Metallic Parts: A Review, *Metals and Materials International* 27(1) (2021) 1-39.
- [6] D. Svetlizky, M. Das, B. Zheng, A.L. Vyatskikh, S. Bose, A. Bandyopadhyay, J.M. Schoenung, E.J. Lavernia, N. Eliaz, Directed energy deposition (DED) additive manufacturing: Physical characteristics, defects, challenges and applications, *Materials Today* 49 (2021) 271-295.
- [7] L. Guo, L. Zhang, J. Andersson, O. Ojo, Additive manufacturing of 18% nickel maraging steels: Defect, structure and mechanical properties: A review, *Journal of Materials Science & Technology* 120 (2022) 227-252.
- [8] T. DebRoy, H.L. Wei, J.S. Zuback, T. Mukherjee, J.W. Elmer, J.O. Milewski, A.M. Beese, A. Wilson-Heid, A. De, W. Zhang, Additive manufacturing of metallic components – Process, structure and properties, *Progress in Materials Science* 92 (2018) 112-224.
- [9] C. Tan, K. Zhou, W. Ma, P. Zhang, M. Liu, T. Kuang, Microstructural evolution, nanoprecipitation behavior and mechanical properties of selective laser melted high-performance grade 300 maraging steel, *Materials & Design* 134 (2017) 23-34.
- [10] M. Roudnická, O. Molnárová, D. Dvorský, L. Křivský, D. Vojtěch, Specific Response of Additively Manufactured AlSi9Cu3Fe Alloy to Precipitation Strengthening, *Metals and Materials International* 26(8) (2020) 1168-1181.
- [11] F.F. Conde, J.A. Avila, J.P. Oliveira, N. Schell, M.F. Oliveira, J.D. Escobar, Effect of the as-built microstructure on the martensite to austenite transformation in a 18Ni maraging steel after laser-based powder bed fusion, *Additive Manufacturing* 46 (2021) 102122.
- [12] S.M. Thompson, L. Bian, N. Shamsaei, A. Yadollahi, An overview of Direct Laser Deposition for additive manufacturing; Part I: Transport phenomena, modeling and diagnostics, *Additive Manufacturing* 8 (2015) 36-62.
- [13] C. Tan, K. Zhou, M. Kuang, W. Ma, T. Kuang, Microstructural characterization and properties of selective laser melted maraging steel with different build directions, *Science and Technology of Advanced Materials* 19(1) (2018) 746-758.
- [14] D. Fonseca, A. M. Feitosa, M. Feitosa, L. De Carvalho, R. Lesley, A. Padilha, A Short Review on Ultra-High-Strength Maraging Steels and Future Perspectives, *Materials Research* 24 (2021) 20200470.
- [15] Y. Yao, Y. Huang, B. Chen, C. Tan, Y. Su, J. Feng, Influence of processing parameters and heat treatment on the mechanical properties of 18Ni300 manufactured by laser based directed energy deposition, *Optics & Laser Technology* 105 (2018) 171-179.
- [16] E.A. Jäggle, Z. Sheng, P. Kürnsteiner, S. Ocylok, A. Weisheit, D. Raabe, Comparison of Maraging Steel Micro- and Nanostructure Produced Conventionally and by Laser Additive Manufacturing, *Materials* 10(1) (2017).
- [17] S. Bodziak, K.S. Al-Rubaie, L.D. Valentina, F.H. Lafratta, E.C. Santos, A.M. Zanatta, Y. Chen, Precipitation in 300 grade maraging steel built by selective laser melting: Aging at 510 °C for 2 h, *Materials Characterization* 151 (2019) 73-83.
- [18] Y. Bai, D. Wang, Y. Yang, H. Wang, Effect of heat treatment on the microstructure and mechanical properties of maraging steel by selective laser melting, *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 760 (2019) 105-117.
- [19] R. Casati, J.N. Lemke, A. Tuissi, M. Vedani, Aging Behaviour and Mechanical Performance of 18-Ni 300 Steel Processed by Selective Laser Melting, *Metals* 6(9) (2016).
- [20] L. Guo, L. Zhang, J. Andersson, O. Ojo, Effect of heat treatment on mechanical compression properties of C250 maraging steel fabricated by directed energy deposition, *Materials Characterization* 209 (2024) 113778.
- [21] V.K. Vasudevan, S.J. Kim, C.M. Wayman, Precipitation reactions and strengthening behavior in 18 Wt Pct nickel maraging steels, *Metallurgical transactions. A, Physical metallurgy and materials science* 21 A(10) (1990) 2655-2668.
- [22] X. Xu, S. Ganguly, J. Ding, S. Guo, S. Williams, F. Martina, Microstructural evolution and mechanical properties of maraging steel produced by wire+arc additive manufacture process, *Materials Characterization* 143 (2018) 152-162.

- [23] M.N. Rao, Progress in understanding the metallurgy of 18% nickel maraging steels, 97(11) (2006) 1594-1607.
- [24] A. Strakosova, F. Průša, A. Michalcová, P. Kratochvíl, D. Vojtěch, Annealing Response of Additively Manufactured High-Strength 1.2709 Maraging Steel Depending on Elevated Temperatures, *Materials* 15(11) (2022).
- [25] A.R. Oliveira, J.A.A. Diaz, A.D.C. Nizes, A.L. Jardini, E.G. Del Conte, Investigation of Building Orientation and Aging on Strength–Stiffness Performance of Additively Manufactured Maraging Steel, *Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance* 30(2) (2021) 1479-1489.
- [26] T.H. Becker, D. Dimitrov, The achievable mechanical properties of SLM produced Maraging Steel 300 components, *Rapid Prototyping Journal* 22(3) (2016) 487-494.
- [27] A. Suzuki, R. Nishida, N. Takata, M. Kobashi, M. Kato, Design of laser parameters for selectively laser melted maraging steel based on deposited energy density, *Additive Manufacturing* 28 (2019) 160-168.
- [28] G. Casalino, S.L. Campanelli, N. Contuzzi, A.D. Ludovico, Experimental investigation and statistical optimisation of the selective laser melting process of a maraging steel, *Optics & Laser Technology* 65 (2015) 151-158.
- [29] D. Rigon, G. Meneghetti, M. Görtler, D. Cozzi, W. Waldhauser, M. Dabalà, Influence of defects on axial fatigue strength of maraging steel specimens produced by additive manufacturing, *MATEC Web Conf.* 165 (2018).
- [30] J. Mutua, S. Nakata, T. Onda, Z.-C. Chen, Optimization of selective laser melting parameters and influence of post heat treatment on microstructure and mechanical properties of maraging steel, *Materials & Design* 139 (2018) 486-497.
- [31] Y. Bai, Y. Yang, D. Wang, M. Zhang, Influence mechanism of parameters process and mechanical properties evolution mechanism of maraging steel 300 by selective laser melting, *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 703 (2017) 116-123.
- [32] F. Zhou, R. Wu, W. Xie, L. Zhang, Effect of aging treatment on microstructure and properties of additively manufactured maraging steel, *Ironmaking & Steelmaking* 47(9) (2020) 980-985.
- [33] A. Strakosova, J. Kubásek, A. Michalcová, F. Průša, D. Vojtěch, D. Dvorský, High Strength X3NiCoMoTi 18-9-5 Maraging Steel Prepared by Selective Laser Melting from Atomized Powder, *Materials* 12(24) (2019).
- [34] S.L. Campanelli, N. Contuzzi, P. Posa, A. Angelastro, Study of the aging treatment on selective laser melted maraging 300 steel, *Materials Research Express* 6(6) (2019) 066580.
- [35] H. Hou, H. Li, Y. Jin, X. Wang, Z. Wen, Effect of heat treatment temperature on the mechanical properties of low-temperature high strength maraging steel, *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 601 (2014) 1-6.
- [36] B. Mooney, K.I. Kourousis, R. Raghavendra, D. Agius, Process phenomena influencing the tensile and anisotropic characteristics of additively manufactured maraging steel, *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 745 (2019) 115-125.
- [37] W.F. Guo, C. Guo, Q. Zhu, Heat treatment behavior of the 18ni300 maraging steel additively manufactured by selective laser melting, *Materials Science Forum*, 2018, pp. 2160-2166.
- [38] K. Kempen, E. Yasa, L. Thijs, J.P. Kruth, J. Van Humbeeck, Microstructure and mechanical properties of Selective Laser Melted 18Ni-300 steel, *Physics Procedia* 12 (2011) 255-263.
- [39] S. Dehgahi, M. Sanjari, M.H. Ghoncheh, B.S. Amirkhiz, M. Mohammadi, Concurrent improvement of strength and ductility in heat-treated C300 maraging steels produced by laser powder bed fusion technique, *Additive Manufacturing* 39 (2021) 101847.
- [40] T. Tekin, G. Ischia, F. Naclerio, R. Ipek, A. Molinari, Effect of a direct aging heat treatment on the microstructure and the tensile properties of a 18Ni-300 maraging steel produced by Laser Powder Bed Fusion, *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 872 (2023) 144921.
- [41] S. Amirabdollahian, F. Deirmina, L. Harris, R. Siriki, M. Pellizzari, P. Bosetti, A. Molinari, Towards controlling intrinsic heat treatment of maraging steel during laser directed energy deposition, *Scripta Materialia* 201 (2021) 113973.

- [42] b. Chen, Y. Huang, T. Gu, C. Tan, J. Feng, Investigation on the process and microstructure evolution during direct laser metal deposition of 18Ni300, *Rapid Prototyping Journal* 24 (2018).
- [43] T.D. Truong, G. Asala, O.T. Ola, O.A. Ojo, A.G. Odeshi, Texture and damage evolution in additively manufactured 18 %Ni-M350 maraging steel under dynamic impact loading: Processing parameters and heat treatment effects, *Materialia* 32 (2023) 101961.
- [44] J. Jeong, G.W. No, H.J. Bae, S.K. Yoo, I.-C. Choi, H.S. Kim, J.B. Seol, J.G. Kim, Mechanical properties of lamellar-structured 18Ni300 maraging steel manufactured via directed energy deposition, *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 892 (2024) 146031.
- [45] G. Asala, O.T. Ola, O.A. Ojo, Effects of process variables on the quality and mechanical properties of 18%Ni-M350 maraging steel produced by direct energy deposition laser additive manufacturing, *Materials Science and Engineering: A* 866 (2023) 144646.
- [46] M. Klinger, More features, more tools, more CrysTBox, *Journal of Applied Crystallography* 50 (2017).
- [47] K. Kassym, A. Perveen, Atomization processes of metal powders for 3D printing, *Materials Today: Proceedings* 26 (2020) 1727-1733.
- [48] P. Ren, Y. Ouyang, J. Mu, S. Luo, Z. Tang, Y. Wu, C.L.A. Leung, J.P. Oliveira, Y. Zou, H. Wang, H. Wang, Metal powder atomization preparation, modification, and reuse for additive manufacturing: A review, *Progress in Materials Science* 152 (2025) 101449.
- [49] H.D. Nguyen, A. Pramanik, A.K. Basak, Y. Dong, C. Prakash, S. Debnath, S. Shankar, I.S. Jawahir, S. Dixit, D. Buddhi, A critical review on additive manufacturing of Ti-6Al-4V alloy: microstructure and mechanical properties, *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 18 (2022) 4641-4661.
- [50] A.M. Mullis, L. Farrell, R.F. Cochrane, N.J. Adkins, Estimation of Cooling Rates During Close-Coupled Gas Atomization Using Secondary Dendrite Arm Spacing Measurement, *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions B* 44(4) (2013) 992-999.
- [51] S. Yin, C. Chen, X. Yan, X. Feng, R. Jenkins, P. O'Reilly, M. Liu, H. Li, R. Lupoi, The influence of aging temperature and aging time on the mechanical and tribological properties of selective laser melted maraging 18Ni-300 steel, *Additive Manufacturing* 22 (2018) 592-600.
- [52] R. Snell, S. Tammam-Williams, L. Chechik, A. Lyle, E. Hernández-Nava, C. Boig, G. Panoutsos, I. Todd, Methods for Rapid Pore Classification in Metal Additive Manufacturing, *JOM* 72(1) (2020) 101-109.
- [53] S. Liu, Y.C. Shin, Additive manufacturing of Ti6Al4V alloy: A review, *Materials & Design* 164 (2019) 107552.
- [54] F.F. Conde, J.D. Escobar, J.P. Oliveira, A.L. Jardini, W.W. Bose Filho, J.A. Avila, Austenite reversion kinetics and stability during tempering of an additively manufactured maraging 300 steel, *Additive Manufacturing* 29 (2019) 100804.
- [55] K. Gangaraju, H. Kim, Heterogeneous Aspects of Additive Manufactured Metallic Parts: A Review, *Metals and Materials International* 27 (2021).
- [56] J. Suryawanshi, K.G. Prashanth, U. Ramamurty, Tensile, fracture, and fatigue crack growth properties of a 3D printed maraging steel through selective laser melting, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 725 (2017) 355-364.
- [57] R.I. Revilla, G. Li, R. Pion, K. Marcoen, F. Andreatta, L. Fedrizzi, K. Vanmeensel, I. De Graeve, Effect of heat treatment on the microstructure and pitting corrosion behavior of 316L stainless steel fabricated by different additive manufacturing methods (L-PBF versus L-DED): Comparative investigation exploring the role of microstructural features on passivity, *Corrosion Science* 228 (2024) 111814.
- [58] S. Felicioni, A. Aversa, E. Librera, F. Bondioli, P. Fino, Directed energy deposition of 18NiM300 steel: effect of process and post processing conditions on microstructure and properties, *Science and Technology of Advanced Materials* 25(1) (2024) 2346071.
- [59] A. Magnee, J.M. Drapier, D. Coutsouradis, L. Habrakan, J. Dumont, Cobalt-containing high-strength steels, 1974.
- [60] A.C.d.F. Silveira, R. Fechte-Heinen, J. Epp, Microstructure evolution during laser-directed energy deposition of tool steel by in situ synchrotron X-ray diffraction, *Additive Manufacturing* 63 (2023) 103408.
- [61] A. Strakosova, M. Roudnická, J. Šafka, M. Ackermann, D. Dvorský, A. Školáková, M. Vronka, P. Svora, J. Drahoukoupil, J. Pinc, J. Maňák, O. Ekrt, Z. Weiss, V. Mazáčová, P. Lejček, Effect of titanium on

- microstructure and mechanical behaviour of additively manufactured 1.2709 maraging steel, *Additive Manufacturing* 88 (2024) 104264.
- [62] M. Król, P. Snopiński, A. Czech, The phase transitions in selective laser-melted 18-Ni (300-grade) maraging steel, *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry* 142(2) (2020) 1011-1018.
- [63] A.G.d. Reis, D.A.P. Reis, A.J. Abdalla, J. Otubo, High-temperature creep resistance and effects on the austenite reversion and precipitation of 18 Ni (300) maraging steel, *Materials Characterization* 107 (2015) 350-357.
- [64] B. Mooney, K.I. Kourousis, R. Raghavendra, Plastic anisotropy of additively manufactured maraging steel: Influence of the build orientation and heat treatments, *Additive Manufacturing* 25 (2019) 19-31.
- [65] A. Strakosova, M. Roudnická, O. Ekrt, D. Vojtěch, A. Michalcová, Hydrogen Embrittlement of the Additively Manufactured High-Strength X3NiCoMoTi 18-9-5 Maraging Steel, *Materials* 14(17) (2021).
- [66] G. Stornelli, D. Gaggia, M. Rallini, A. Di Schino, HEAT TREATMENT EFFECT ON MARAGING STEEL MANUFACTURED BY LASER POWDER BED FUSION TECHNOLOGY: MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES, *Acta Metallurgica Slovaca* 27(3) (2021) 122-126.
- [67] J. Hu, L.-X. Du, Y. Dong, Q.-W. Meng, R.D.K. Misra, Effect of Ti variation on microstructure evolution and mechanical properties of low carbon medium Mn heavy plate steel, *Materials Characterization* 152 (2019) 21-35.
- [68] D. Wang, R. Su, H. Li, C. Wang, J. Guo, Z. Li, H. Zeng, H. Chen, Effect of Ti content on the strengthening and fracture damage mechanism of mechanical properties of weathering steel, *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 30 (2024) 3690-3704.
- [69] X. Zhu, J. Yang, S. Wang, S. Bu, M. Shen, X. Miao, X. Li, The investigation of precipitation behavior of titanium compounds for high titanium steel based on in situ observation, *PLOS ONE* 18 (2023) e0275049.
- [70] F. Huang, Z. Cheng, D. Zhang, D. Qian, Y. Liu, Z. Hu, L. Hua, A novel process for simultaneously improving the strength and plasticity of 18Ni(350) maraging steel, *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 33 (2024) 6144-6156.
- [71] M. Niu, G. Zhou, W. Wang, M.B. Shahzad, Y. Shan, K. Yang, Precipitate evolution and strengthening behavior during aging process in a 2.5 GPa grade maraging steel, *Acta Materialia* 179 (2019) 296-307.
- [72] T. Mukherjee, J.W. Elmer, H.L. Wei, T.J. Lienert, W. Zhang, S. Kou, T. DebRoy, Control of grain structure, phases, and defects in additive manufacturing of high-performance metallic components, *Progress in Materials Science* 138 (2023) 101153.